

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SKULL NAMES IN UZBEK AND LATIN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: In the article, the advantages of the most important "language experience" method of foreign language teaching, the time of its use, and the expected results, based on my pedagogical work experience and deep conclusions of scientific-theoretical, scientific-practical correspondence, this method is used to learn the professional Latin language in medical universities of our Republic. An attempt was made to make a written statement with the help of examples that confirm the opinions that justify the effectiveness of teaching and learning.

Key words: bone, skull, part of the brain, skeleton, oral cavity, skull cap

Skull, head skeleton (Latin: cranium) - the head skeleton of vertebrates and humans. In adults, the cranium is united by sutures, and in babies there is a non-ossified part between these bones - ligules. The human skull consists of 23 bones, some of them are even and some are odd. Due to the highly developed brain in humans, the brain part of the cranium (skull box) is large, the facial part extends down, and in animals, the facial part is extended forward and forms the main part of the cranium. The skull is the support of the brain and the sensory organs developed with it, protecting them from the influence of the external environment. In addition to these, in the facial part of the skull, the beginning of the respiratory system - the nasal cavity, the beginning of the digestive system - the oral cavity, and hearing and balance organs, which are important for the body's life, are located.

The brain compartment of the skull is bounded from the top by the skull cap, and consists of the cranial cavity inside which the brain is located. The cranial cavity is the widened end of the spinal canal where the brain is enclosed by membranes. Nerves (optic, filter, trigeminal, facial, auditory nerves, etc.) and blood vessels (carotid arteries, jugular veins) pass through holes in the base of the skull. The temporal bone contains the middle ear cavity and the inner ear. The pituitary gland is located in the Turkish saddle at the base of the middle of the skull. The medulla oblongata is located in the occiput. The medulla descends into the spinal cord through the occipital foramen, the largest opening at the base of the skull.

Each bone that forms the dome of the skull consists of 2 plates: the outer plate is thicker, the inner (facing the brain) plate is brittle and brittle (also called

the vitreous plate) and can break when the head is hit (even if the outer plate is not damaged) and the meninges can tear and bleed or injure the brain, which is life-threatening. Therefore, K. s. in case of damage, it is difficult to make a definite conclusion without examining it on X-ray, without determining the condition of the inner plate of the skull. Between the 2 plates of the skull there is a thin porous substance and venous channels. A blood vessel passing through the canal connects the venous sinuses formed by the membranes in the brain cavity with the cutaneous veins covering the skull. These veins keep the blood flow in the brain cavity at the same level. Sometimes, when the scalp is injured, it is necessary to take immediate action, otherwise germs can pass from the injured area to the brain through blood vessels and cause many unpleasant situations. The brain part of the skull is made up of the occipital bone, the frontal bone, a pair of parietal bones, a pons, a calvarial bone and a pair of temporal bones.

The facial part of the skull consists of the upper jaw, a pair of palates, cheeks, nose, lacrimal, mandible, tibia, and lower jaw and sublingual bones. These bones (except the mandible) articulate with each other, and the mandible is joined by a joint.

The brain part of a newborn baby's head is larger than the face part; ossification begins directly from the period of the membrane, as a result, in babies, there are parts covered by the membrane between the bones. During childbirth, the skull folds like a harmonica, making birth easier. Babies can ossify from 2-3 months to one year old. When ossification is delayed, children should be given fish oil and taken outdoors more. The skull is too big (macrocephaly) or too small (microcephaly), different shapes (oblong, round, etc.), and it has been scientifically proven that different sizes do not affect a person's intelligence in any way.

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